

Efficiency evaluation of Amlodipine combined with N-acetylcysteine on Indomethacin-induced gastritis in rats

Yara Annouf¹, Shaza Al laham^{1,2}, Eyad Chatty³

1 *Damascus University, Faculty of Pharmacy, Al Mazzeh, Damascus, Syria*

2 *Syrian Private University, Faculty of Pharmacy, Deir Ali, Daraa, Syria*

3 *Damascus University, Faculty of Medicine, Al Mazzeh, Damascus, Syria*

Corresponding author: Yara Annouf (yara.anouf93@gmail.com)

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Abstract

Introduction: It is a well-known phenomenon that nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs cause gastric mucosal damage. **Amlodipine** is a third generation dihydropyridine-type calcium channel blocker; it can inhibit inflammatory cytokines and enhance antioxidant defenses. **N-acetylcysteine** can act both as a precursor of reduced glutathione and as a direct ROS scavenger. Moreover, **N-acetylcysteine** has been purported to have anti-inflammatory properties.

Materials and methods: 34 albino Wistar rats were used. The model of gastritis was induced by subcutaneous **Indomethacin** prepared in 5% **sodium bicarbonate** administered at a dose rate of 9 mg/kg for two days at 24h intervals. **N-acetylcysteine** (500 mg/kg), **Amlodipine** (10 mg/kg) and **N-acetylcysteine** (500 mg/kg) combined with **Amlodipine** (5 mg/kg) were administrated for seven consecutive days beginning 24 h after the first **Indomethacin** injection. Rats were sacrificed under ether anesthesia on the 8th day. The stomach injury was assessed by macroscopic damage and histological study.

Results and discussion: The results showed that macroscopic stomach damage scores caused by administration of **Indomethacin** did not significantly decrease by administration of **N-acetylcysteine** alone ($p>0.05$), but it decreased significantly by administration of **Amlodipine** alone or by its combination with **N-acetylcysteine** ($p<0.05$). Microscopic stomach damage scores did not significantly decrease by administration of **Amlodipine** or **N-acetylcysteine** alone ($p>0.05$), but they decreased significantly by administering the combination of **Amlodipine** with **N-acetylcysteine** ($p<0.05$). Administration of **Amlodipine** with **N-acetylcysteine** showed significant reduction in the severity of the gastric inflammation induced by **Indomethacin**, which was evidenced macroscopically and microscopically.

Conclusion: This study concluded that administration of **Amlodipine** with **N-acetylcysteine** produce obvious enhancement in gastritis induced by **Indomethacin**.

Graphical abstract:**Keywords**

Amlodipine, gastritis, histological study, macroscopic damage, N-acetylcysteine, Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.

Introduction

The term gastritis has been used loosely to clarify vague endoscopic findings of the gastric mucosa (eg. erythema, nodularity, and erosions) and additionally to elucidate gastric inflammation from mucosal injury. Accurately, gastritis refers to the microscopic returns of gastric mucosal injury with inflammation (Francis 2008). Infectious (*Helicobacter pylori*), chemical, and autoimmune are the most common shapes of gastritis (Rugge and Graham 2016). Chemical gastropathy may be seen in three clinical settings: postgastrectomy alkaline reflux; bile reflux secondary to gastroduodenal dysmotility; and administration of aspirin or NSAID (Washington and Peek 2009).

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are thought to be the most widely used drug group worldwide (Hawkins 2000). It is a well-known phenomenon that NSAIDs cause gastric mucosal damage resulting in consequences ranging from nonspecific dyspepsia to ulceration, upper gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding and death – summarized by the term ‘NSAID gastropathy’ (Becker et al. 2004).

The conventional view is that NSAID-induced mucosal damage results from inhibition of cyclo-oxygenase with consequent weakness of reparative prostaglandin generation. NSAIDs may also affect the gastric mucosal barrier by altering mucus and bicarbonate secretion and by intervening with mucosal blood flow (Quinn et al. 1993). In addition to inhibiting cyclooxygenase and decreasing prostaglandin production, NSAIDs

stimulate mucosal damage *via* ROS produced by recruited leukocytes. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) lead to apoptosis and mucosal injury by mitochondrial damage as well as lipid, protein, and DNA damage (Suzuki et al. 2012).

Amlodipine is a third generation dihydropyridine-type calcium channel blocker commonly used for the treatment of hypertension (Mohammed et al. 2016). Experimental studies have shown that **Amlodipine** can inhibit inflammatory cytokines and boost antioxidant defenses (El Morsy et al. 2015).

N-acetylcysteine (NAC), a precursor of reduced glutathione (GSH), has been used clinically for more than 30 years, primarily as a mucolytic. **NAC** is also used in conditions characterized by decreased GSH or oxidative stress (Kelly 1998). Moreover, NAC has been purported to have anti-inflammatory properties. **NAC** inhibits induction of the Activator Protein-1 (AP-1) and NF- κ B (Atalay et al. 2016).

The present study highlights the effect of **Amlodipine** combined with **N-acetylcysteine** on Indomethacin-induced gastritis in rats.

Materials and methods**Materials**

Indomethacin (FarmaSino Pharmaceuticals, Jiangsu, China), **N-acetylcysteine** (Wuhan Grand Hoyo Company Ltd, China), **Amlodipine** (Prudence Pharma Chem, Ankleshwar, India).

Animals and experimental design

Wistar albino rats weighing 160–290 g were purchased from the Scientific Research Center, Damascus, Syria. The animals were supplied with ad libitum feed and water. The animals were kept under the controlled environmental conditions (temperature 23 ± 2 °C, humidity $55\pm 15\%$, lighting regimen of 12h light:12h dark). They were adapted for one week before any experiments.

The animals were randomly divided into five groups:

Group I: 6 rats received the vehicle (physiological saline) orally and served as normal control group.

Group II: 7 rats received subcutaneous **Indomethacin** prepared in 5% **sodium bicarbonate**, administered at a dose rate of 9 mg/kg for two days at 24h intervals and served as **Indomethacin** control group (Annouf et al. 2020). It also received physiological saline orally.

Group III: 8 rats were administered **N-acetylcysteine** dissolved in physiological saline (500 mg/kg body weight, po) (Lee and Kang 2019) for seven consecutive days, beginning 24h after the first **Indomethacin** injection.

Group IV: 6 rats were administered **Amlodipine** dissolved in physiological saline (10 mg/kg body weight, po) (El Morsy et al. 2015) for seven consecutive days, beginning 24h after the first **Indomethacin** injection.

Group V: 7 rats were administered 500 mg/kg of **N-acetylcysteine** plus 5 mg/kg of **Amlodipine** for seven consecutive days, beginning 24h after the first **Indomethacin** injection.

Groups III, IV and V were given 9 mg/kg of subcutaneous **Indomethacin** for two days at 24h intervals.

On the 8th day, each sub group of animals across all groups was sacrificed. The stomach was isolated and was opened along greater curvature, then washed in saline solution and any macroscopic change was checked. A precise evaluation of the lesions was made after each specimen was fixed in 10% **formalin**.

Macroscopic score

All macroscopic evaluations were performed just after scarification of the rats and before sending half of the stomach to the physiology laboratory (Sabiou et al. 2015) (Table 1).

Table 1. Macroscopic inflammation assessment of the stomach

Score	Remark
0	Almost normal mucosa
1	Vascular congestions
2	One or two lesions
3	Severe lesions
4	Very severe lesions
5	Mucosa full of lesions

Histopathological observations

Tissue samples were collected from one half of the stomach and were kept for histologic assessment. Five micrometer sections were gained from paraffin-embedded tissues and stained with hematoxylin and eosin. Tissue slides were tested under a light microscope.

The following histological features were examined by an unbiased pathologist blinded to the experimental design: grade and type of inflammation, extension of inflammation throughout the gastrointestinal wall (mucosa, submucosa, muscular layer and serous membrane), existence of lymphatic follicle, necrosis, granuloma, cryptitis, crypt abscess, and epithelial lesions (erosions, ulcers) (Nakhai et al. 2007) (Table 2).

Table 2. Microscopic inflammation assessment of the stomach

Criteria	Score
Increased inflammatory infiltration	0 (none)
	1 (mild)
	2 (moderate)
	3 (severe)
Lymphoid aggregate/follicle	0 (none)
	1 (recognized)
Necrosis	0 (none)
	1 (recognized)
Granuloma	0 (none)
	1 (recognized)
Cryptitis	0 (none)
	1 (recognized)
Crypt abscess	0 (none)
	1 (recognized)
Erosions	0 (none)
	1 (recognized)
Ulcers	0 (none)
	1 (recognized)
Transmural inflammation	0 (none)
	1 (recognized)
Maximum score	11

Statistical analysis

Data analyses were done using a software program Graph Pad Prism version 8. Data were expressed as mean $\pm$ SEM, and different groups were compared using Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's test for multiple comparisons for non-parametric data. P values were considered statistically significant when they were less than 0.05.

Results

Macroscopic score

No stomach sections from normal control group revealed any morphological changes. In contrast, subcutaneous injection of **Indomethacin** caused damage in the stomach. Vascular congestions, hemorrhagic spots, and erosions were noticed. The morphological score in the

Indomethacin control group was significantly increased ($p=0.0020$) as compared to normal control group.

The group treated with **Amlodipine** reduced the severity of the gross lesion. There was statistical significance when compared with **Indomethacin** control group ($p=0.0186$).

NAC-treated group reduced the severity of the macroscopic score, but there was no statistical significance when compared with **Indomethacin** control group ($p=0.0685$).

Amlodipine-combined-with-NAC-treated group revealed reduction in the severity of the gross lesion. There was statistical significance when compared with **Indomethacin**-treated group ($p=0.0060$), but there was no statistical significance when compared with Amlodipine-treated

Table 3. Macroscopic score of different experimental groups

Group	Normal control group	INDO control group	NAC treated group	AML treated group	AML+NAC treated group
0	6 (100%)	1 (14.29%)	4 (50%)	5 (83.33%)	7 (100%)
1		4 (57.14%)	4 (50%)		
2		2 (28.57%)		1 (16.67%)	
3					
4					
5					

Note: INDO - Indomethacin, NAC - N-acetylcysteine, AML - Amlodipine

Figure 1. Macroscopic appearance of the stomach: **a.** Normal control group (score=0); **b.** Indomethacin control group (score=2); **c.** Amlodipine-treated group (score=0); **d.** N-acetylcysteine-treated group (score=1); **e.** Amlodipine+N-acetylcysteine-treated group (score=0).

group ($p=0.7730$), and NAC-treated group ($p=0.1630$) (Table 3) (Fig. 1).

Microscopic score

The stomach specimen of all rats from normal control group revealed an intact architecture. On the other hand,

Figure 2. Effect of **N-acetylcysteine** combined with **Amlodipine** on macroscopic score in Indomethacin-induced gastritis in rats. Data are expressed as mean $\pm$ SEM. Note: ** - Significant difference as compared to normal control group at $p<0.01$; # - Significant difference as compared to Indomethacin control group at $p<0.05$; ## - Significant difference as compared to Indomethacin control group at $p<0.01$; INDO - Indomethacin, NAC - N-acetylcysteine, AML - Amlodipine.

the stomach specimen of **Indomethacin** control group revealed increased inflammatory cell infiltration; the inflammation was mild to moderate; it also revealed lymphatic follicle and cryptitis in some of them. There was statistical significance when compared with normal control group ($p=0.0084$).

Administration of **Amlodipine** as therapy revealed in some rats reduction in the severity of the in the stomach injury with no statistical significance when compared with **Indomethacin** control group ($p=0.0989$).

Administration of **NAC** as therapy also revealed in some rats reduction in the severity of the stomach injury with no statistical significance when compared with **Indomethacin** control group ($p=0.3101$).

Administration of Amlodipine with **NAC** revealed reduction in the severity of the stomach injury (Fig. 3) (Table 4) with statistical significance when compared with **Indomethacin** control group ($p=0.0095$), but no statistical significance was observed when compared either with NAC-treated group ($p=0.0958$), or with Amlodipine-treated group ($p=0.3990$) (Fig. 4).

Discussion

The NSAID-related gastroduodenal injury is very frequent and the most dangerous complication of any drug therapy. The NSAID gastropathy is considered a "silent epidemic" and, therefore, has been an area of intense research. Among the commonly used NSAIDs, **Indomethacin** (INDO) possesses the highest ulcerogenic potential to humans. The major reason for gastric pathogenesis caused by NSAIDs including **INDO** is reduced prostaglandin (PG) synthesis by inhibition of the cyclooxygenases (COXs) (Yadav et al. 2012). There are principally three different mechanisms of NSAID-induced GI complications: inhibition of enzyme COX-1 and gastroprotective PG,

Figure 3. Histological appearance of stomach tissue sections, original magnification $\times 10$. Note: **a.** Normal control group (grade 0) shows an intact architecture; **b.** Indomethacin control group (grade 3) shows focal cryptitis and increased inflammatory cells infiltration; **c.** Amlodipine-treated group (grade 2) shows non specific chronic inflammation; **d.** N-acetylcysteine (500 mg/kg) treated group (grade 2) shows increased inflammatory cells infiltration; **e.** Amlodipine+N-acetylcysteine-treated group (grade 0) shows an intact architecture.

Table 4. Microscopic score of different experimental groups

Group	Normal control group	INDO control group	NAC treated group	AML treated group	AML+NAC treated group
0	6 (100%)	1 (14.29%)	3 (37.5%)	4 (66.67%)	6 (85.71%)
1		2 (28.57%)	2 (25%)		
2		2 (28.57%)	2 (25%)	1 (16.66%)	1 (14.29%)
3		2 (28.57%)	1 (12.5%)	1 (16.66%)	
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					

Note: **INDO** - Indomethacin, **NAC** - N-acetylcysteine, **AML** - Amlodipine.

membrane permeabilization, and production of additional proinflammatory mediators (Sinha et al. 2013). **INDO** is a known inducer of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species in animal models, which may contribute to mucosal injury (Yadav et al. 2012). Till now, no effective treatment has been yet developed for addressing the NSAID-related gastric damage (Sinha et al. 2013).

Amlodipine is a calcium channel blocker (Sheraz et al. 2016). All the knowledge from the literature shows that calcium ions play the main role in the synthesis and release of inflammatory mediators which cause inflammation (Unlu et al. 2013). Therefore, a decrease in intracellular calcium levels may prevent or reduce inflammation. **Amlodipine** exerts anti oxidative effects in vitro and in vivo by inhibiting the oxidizability of the cell membrane and low-density lipoproteins. This effect was mediated by

Figure 4. Effect of **N-acetylcysteine** combined with **Amlodipine** on microscopic score in Indomethacin-induced gastritis in rats. Data are expressed as mean $\pm$ SEM. Note: ****** - Significant difference as compared to normal control group at $p < 0.01$; **##** - Significant difference as compared to Indomethacin control group at $p < 0.01$; **INDO** - Indomethacin, **NAC** - N-acetylcysteine, **AML** - Amlodipine.

removal free radicals due to its highly lipophilic properties and its chemical structure (El Morsy et al. 2015).

N-acetylcysteine is a source of sulfhydryl groups in cells and a scavenger of free radicals as it interacts with reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as hydrogen peroxide and hydroxyl radical. Therefore, **NAC** has an important role in prevention of oxidative stress (Hou et al. 2015). There are several reports about the role of **NAC** in inflammation. In vitro studies report on the inhibitory effect of **NAC** on a series of inflammatory cytokines, inflammatory cell accumulation and migration (Sadowska and Backer 2007). **NAC** used at clinically obtainable concentrations can inhibit both neutrophil and monocyte chemotaxis. The inhibition of chemotaxis by **NAC** was pH- and concentration-dependent (Kharazmi and Nielsen 1988). **NAC** inhibits the induction of the Activator Protein-1 (AP-1) and NF- κ B. These transcription factors are induced in response to oxidative stress, supporting the argument that the anti-inflammatory properties of **NAC** are due to its mechanism of action as an antioxidant (Atalay et al. 2016).

This study highlights the effect of **Amlodipine** combined with **N-acetylcysteine** on NSAIDs-induced gastritis in rats.

In this study, Indomethacin-induced gastritis was revealed macroscopically and microscopically. Administration of **Amlodipine** alone showed significant reduction in the severity of the macroscopic score, but it cause no significant reduction in the severity of microscopic score. This finding was in discord with many studies, such as the study by Patil et al that showed that **Amlodipine** could reduce the ulcer index and gastric pH in rats with gastric ulcer (Patil et al. 2012). In addition, the study by Behave et al that proved that **Amlodipine** produces a significant protective effect on gastric ulceration and also produces significant anti-ulcer effects when used in combination with famotidine and omeprazole (Bhave et al. 2006).

This study also showed that **N-acetylcysteine** administration alone produced no significant reduction in the

gastric injury induced by **Indomethacin**. There was no significant reduction in the severity of macroscopic and microscopic score when **N-acetylcysteine** was administered alone. This finding was in discord with the study by Farinati et al that revealed that **NAC** is fairly well tolerated and apparently leads to an endoscopic, symptomatic, and to some extent histologic improvement that is not clearly related to changes in mucosal GSH and MDA levels in patients with gastritis and non-ulcer dyspepsia (Farinati et al 1997).

Administration of **Amlodipine** with **NAC** showed significant reduction in the severity of the gastric inflammation induced by **Indomethacin** that was evidenced macroscopically and microscopically.

Conclusion

Administration of **Amlodipine** with **NAC** produces obvious enhancement in gastritis induced by NSAIDs via

anti-inflammatory effects of **NAC** and **Amlodipine**. The study suggests investigation of the effect of this combination on oxidative statuses by procedure of biochemical assays of enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants in the gastric tissues.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interests.

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Author contributions

- **Yara Annouf**, Damascus, Syria, MSc in Pharmacology, researcher at Pharmacology Department, Damascus University; e-mail: yara.annouf93@gmail.com, **ORCID ID** <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6214-9658>. The author was engaged in paper writing and preparing graphical materials.
- **Shaza Al laham**, Damascus, Syria, PhD in Pharmacology, head of Pharmacology and Toxicology Department, Damascus University, working in Damascus University and Syrian private university; e-mail: lahamshaza@gmail.com. The author was engaged in developing the concept and conducting literature analysis.
- **Eyad Chatty**, PhD in Pathology, Damascus University; e-mail: eyadchatty@gamil.com. The author was engaged in developing the concept and conducting literature analysis.